

Kinetics of the Perbenzoic Acid Oxidation of Substituted Chalkones

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The kinetics of the epoxidation of chalcone and substituted chalcones by perbenzoic acid has been studied in benzene solution. The rates are found to be proportional to the concentrations of chalcone and perbenzoic acid. A correlation of σ^+ substituent constants and rate constants has been obtained for the substituents with $\rho^+ = -0.45$. The para resonance interaction values ($\Delta\Delta F_p$ values) have been computed which furnish evidences in support of the transition state. The effect of substituents has also been discussed in terms of the reactivity-selectivity relationship. A suitable mechanism for the epoxidation of chalcones has been proposed in the light of the results.

IN the recent past a number of studies has been devoted to the oxidation of olefins by perbenzoic acid¹. This specific oxidation of an olefin was first discovered by Preleshajew² who showed that perbenzoic acid oxidises olefins in nonpolar solvents to give excellent yield of the corresponding epoxides. The first kinetic studies of the perbenzoic acid oxidation of olefins was studied in 1925 by Boesenken and Blumberger³ in non polar solvents. Considering the relative reactivities of several olefins Robertson and Waters⁴ have suggested that the per acids act by the provision of free hydroxyl cations. Swern⁵ has collected the results of oxidation-velocity data for the Preleshajew reaction and has pointed out that in the oxidation of olefins, $R-CH=CH_2$, the order of reactivity is paralleled by that for bromination under non-polar conditions. Ogata and Tabushi⁶ while studying the kinetics of epoxidation of olefins by perbenzoic acid, have evaluated the effect of substituent on α -methyl stilbenes and stilbenes and discussed the result in terms of the asymmetric attack of perbenzoic acid on the double bond of the olefin. It is well established that oxygen in the peroxy acid acts as an electrophile, in the oxidation of $-C=C-$ bond and as a nucleophile in Baeyer-Villiger oxidation¹ of $C=O$. A kinetic study of the oxidation of various substituted chalcones (phenyl styryl ketone) was undertaken to study the affect of substituents on the rate of oxidation. The resonance interaction energy values⁷ for various para substituents have been computed and the results have been interpreted in terms of the proposed transition state.

Results and Discussion

Relative Reactivities

The relative reactivities of eight substituted chalcones were studied in benzene. The order of

reactivity of different substituents conform to the following order

Linear free-energy relationship

Correlation of the rate constants for different substituents with σ^+ values⁸ gave a ρ^+ of -0.45 (Fig. 1). The correlation coefficient (r) was 0.9981 and the standard deviation (s) from the regression line was 0.0371. The negative value of ρ^+ indicates that the rate is enhanced by electron repelling groups and retarded by electron attracting groups.

Fig. 1.

A regression line was fitted to the $\log k$ values against σ^+ data⁹ for the meta-substituted compounds. The reaction constant ' ρ ', the correlation coefficient ' r ' and the intercept with the ordinate were found to be -0.39 , 0.998 and 0.55 respectively.

Considering several reaction series and numerous data, it has been suggested by Van Bekkum and

co-authors⁷ that in those cases where a substituent enters into mesomeric para interaction with the reaction centre, a multiplicity of (exalted) sigma values is obtained. This holds for +M as well as -M substituents. But in the absence of mesomeric para interaction sigma values are reasonably constant.

TABLE 1—SECOND ORDER RATE CONSTANTS (1 MOLE⁻¹ SEC⁻¹) FOR EPOXIDATION OF CHALKONE WITH PERBENZOIC ACID IN BENZENE AT 40°

[Chalkone] 10 ² (M)	[PBA] 10 ² (M)	[Benzoic acid] 10 ² (M)	k × 10 ³ lit.mole ⁻¹ sec ⁻¹
2.5	5.0	0	3.65
2.0	4.0	0	3.60
1.5	3.0	0	3.61
1.25	2.5	0	3.58
2.22	2.40	0	3.63
2.5	2.5	5	3.59
2.5	1.25	10	3.59
2.8	1.40	8	3.61

Interpretation of the result in terms of the proposed transition state

The magnitude of the resonance interaction in the transition state is quite small in comparison with, for example, the solvolysis of α, α-4-methyl benzyl chloride¹⁰, a reaction for which ΔΔF_{para} is -1.17 K.Cal/mole and which presumably involves an incipient carbonium ion. But it must be emphasised that the influence of resonance interaction in the transition state is to be judged by the magnitude of such interaction compared with that of the polar contribution to the free energy of activation i.e., by the ratio

$$\Delta\Delta F_p / 2.303 RT\sigma_0 = (\bar{\sigma}) - \sigma_0/\sigma_0$$

The effective σ values and the resonance interaction energy values for both 4-nitro and 4-methoxy group reveal that there is important and substantial resonance interaction between the substituent and the reaction centre in the transition state. This result

TABLE 2—VALUES OF SPECIFIC REACTION RATE FOR SUBSTITUTED CHALKONES
10² × [PBA] = 5M, 10² × [Chalkone] = 2.5 M Solvent = benzene. Temp. = 40°

Substituent	p-OCH ₃	p-CH ₃	m-OCH ₃	H	m-Cl	m-Br	p-Cl	m-NO ₂	p-NO ₂
k × 10 ⁻³ lit.mole ⁻¹ sec ⁻¹	7.43	4.67	4.27	3.65	2.98	2.81	2.11	1.92	1.63

The effective sigma values $\bar{\sigma}$ were calculated from the expression

$$\bar{\sigma} = \log k - \log k_0/\rho$$

As the effective sigma values $\bar{\sigma}$ in general are not suitable criteria for judging mesomeric para interactions, free energy difference terms⁷ have been calculated for evaluation of mesomeric para interactions.

$$\Delta\Delta F_{para} = -2.303 RT\rho(\bar{\sigma} - \sigma^0)$$

This expression involves not only the exaltation of σ (sigma) but of ρ and T as well. The effective sigma values ($\bar{\sigma}$) and the corresponding para resonance energy differences are described in Table 3.

TABLE 3—VALUES OF THE EFFECTIVE SIGMA VALUES, RESONANCE INTERACTION ENERGY VALUES FOR DIFFERENT PARA SUBSTITUENTS

Substituent	p-OCH ₃	p-Cl	p-NO ₂
$\bar{\sigma}$	+0.21	-0.61	-0.88
ΔΔF _p K.Cal/mole	-0.052	+0.19	-0.034

is in good agreement of the transition state which may be represented as follows

The above picture of the transition state is consistent with the negative sign of the ΔΔF_p values for both para methoxy and para nitro groups, which indicates that there is greater resonance interaction in the transition state than in the reactant state⁷. On the basis of the above transition state, the retarding effect of the nitro group can be easily understood, since the nitro group withdraws "pi" electron densities from the -CH = CH- to which the (PBA) adds up.

Reactivity and selectivity relationship

The substituent constants in electrophilic reactions, σ⁺ are given by equation⁶ 1.

$$\sigma^+ = \sigma + r\Delta\sigma_R \quad \dots (1)$$

where r depends on the reaction and on the extent of resonance stabilisation of the carbonium ion in the transition state.

On the other hand, Brown and his co-workers¹¹ showed the linear correlation between the para partial rate factor and the selectivity factor, S_f , defined by

$$S_f = \log(p_f/m_f);$$

$$\log p_f = \alpha x S_f \quad \dots (2)$$

Hence the following equations are derived, where σ_I and σ_R are the inductive and resonance contribution in σ value, respectively.

$$\log p_f = \rho(\sigma_I + \sigma_R + r\Delta R) \quad \dots (3)$$

$$\log m_f = \rho\sigma_I \quad \dots (4)$$

$$S_f = \rho(\sigma_R + r\Delta\sigma_R) \quad \dots (5)$$

On substituting equation, 3, 4 and 5 in equation (2), α can be evaluated as

$$\alpha = \frac{\sigma_I + \sigma_R + r\Delta\sigma_R}{\sigma_R + r\Delta\sigma_R} \quad \dots (6)$$

The value of r and α have been computed by using the above equations, and are described in Table 4.

TABLE 4—VALUES OF r AND α FOR DIFFERENT SUBSTITUENTS

Substituent	-OCH ₃	-NO ₂	-Cl
r	-1.25	+0.483	-6.22
α	+5.13	+4.92	+1.58

The value of α in equation (6) should vary with r . It is evident from our result that the value of α decreases with increase of r , both in electron donating and withdrawing substituents. In other words, in a series of electrophilic reactions, an intermolecular selectivity p_f becomes smaller compared with an increase of r , or the resonance contribution in the transition state. The behaviour of chloro substituent is rather anomalous due to the peculiar characteristics of the substituent.

Mechanism of the reaction

Several mechanisms can be eliminated on the basis of the kinetic results. In preliminary experiments,

a free radical type of mechanism was discarded for the following reasons. Diethyl fumarate, a free radical trap¹² did not change the rate of oxidation and evolution of carbon dioxide was not observed.

The close mechanistic parallel between the perbenzoic acid oxidation of chalcone and reactions with bromine, chromic acid, Tl(III) oxidation is shown by the relative rates of reactions in Table 5.

The similarities of reactivities of different reagents appear that bromine addition, chromic acid, Tl(III) oxidation, peracids all presumably react with carbon carbon double bond via a three membered ring activated complex¹³. Such a partially bridged activated complex can support an increasing positive charge as the electron donating power of the group increases in the phenyl nucleus of the chalcone molecule (C = C double bond). In this respect epoxidation closely resembles chromic acid oxidation¹³, bromine¹⁴⁻¹⁵ and chlorine addition¹⁶ of olefins, i.e., reactions leading to a three membered ring product or intermediate¹⁷.

The direction and magnitude of the substituent effects ($\rho^+ = -0.45$), the resonance interaction energy values for both the methoxy and nitro group are all consistent with such a mechanism.

The conclusions which can be drawn from our results lead us to believe that the rate-limiting step in the perbenzoic acid epoxidation of an olefin is the symmetric electrophilic attack of perbenzoic acid on the double bond leading to an epoxide. Although the transition state for the reaction could be formulated in several different ways, it seems attractive to formulate the reaction similar to the Cr(VI) oxidation of olefin¹³ for which transition state I has been suggested.

The mechanism has the advantage that it assumes the oxygen, transferred to the olefin comes from an OH₂ group which is certainly more electrophilic

TABLE 5—RELATIVE REACTIVITIES OF CHALKONE

	Methoxy mercuration ¹	Tl(III) Oxidation ²	Epoxidation ³	Chromic acid oxidation ⁴	Bromination ⁵
Rate Constant*	1.25×10^{-3}	1.72×10^{-3}	3.60×10^{-3}	10.8×10^{-3}	35.70×10^{-3}

¹ P. L. NAYAK and M. K. ROUT; *Indian J. Chem.* 1970, 8, 722.

² N. C. KHANDUAL, K. K. SATPATHY and P. L. NAYAK; *Z. Phys. Chem.* (Leipzig). Communicated for publication.

³ Present work.

⁴ N. C. KHANDUAL, K. K. SATPATHY and P. L. NAYAK, *J. Chem. Soc. Perkin II*, 1974, 323.

⁵ P. L. NAYAK and M. K. ROUT; *J. Indian Chem. Soc.* 1970, 47, 217.

* Rate constants are expressed in lit.mole⁻¹ sec⁻¹.

than a nonprotonated oxygen and also allows the proton to be transferred intramolecularly by an unstrained cyclic mechanism.

Experimental

The chalkones were prepared and purified by our previous methods¹⁸.

Solvent benzene was purified by treatment with concentrated sulphuric acid and then with sodium. Perbenzoic acid was prepared by methanolysis of benzoyl peroxide¹⁹.

Reaction product

Chalkone was allowed to react overnight with a slight excess of perbenzoic acid under the conditions of rate measurements and at the end of the reaction, the solution was washed with aqueous alkali. The solvent was distilled under vacuum and the residue was crystallised from aqueous ethanol. m.p. 87°.

Anal. Calcd. for $C_{15}H_{12}O_2$ C, 80.35; H, 5.35
found: C, 80.31; H, 5.30.

Method of rate measurement

A benzene solution of chalkone of known concentration, thermostated in brown coloured bottle, was treated with a thermostated solution of perbenzoic acid of known concentration to start the reaction. Aliquots were taken out at appropriate intervals and the remaining perbenzoic acid was estimated by iodometry²⁰.

The rate constants were computed by using a second order equation with the help of least square method.¹¹

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